

Climateurope2

Preliminary best practices in climate uncertainty quantification and communication

Deliverable 2.3

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

This deliverable collects examples of best practices about uncertainty quantification and communication in climate services, largely drawing from existing literature and reports. Examples and best practices were also collected from the Climateurope2 community during an online workshop on communicating climate uncertainty, held in November 2023.

The document is organised in two main parts, discussing the current state-of-the-art and best practices in uncertainty quantification (Chapter 2), and uncertainty communication (Chapter 4). The deliverable also looks into emerging strategies to deal with deep uncertainties, i.e. those that cannot be quantified (Chapter 3), and it also discusses a number of recent real-world examples for assessing, quantifying and communicating uncertainty in climate information (Chapter 5).

A set of eight main lessons learnt regarding preliminary best practices in climate uncertainty assessment and communication can be summarised as follows (see Chapter 6 for more details):

1. Always start with the most relevant risks for the target population
2. A standard approach to uncertainty assessment and communication is needed
3. Use language the audience is familiar with (don't say uncertainty)
4. There are multiple ways to evaluate and communicate uncertainty
5. Communication about uncertainty builds trust
6. Precision of information should be relevant to the situation
7. Understand existing narratives
8. Be aware of deep uncertainties

Update 2025/08 – This update introduces two key additions. First, sections 2.6 and 5.5 now address the influence of timescales on both the evaluation and communication of uncertainty. Second, section 6 incorporates perspectives from a subset of private-sector companies on uncertainty and standardisation.

Keywords

Climate services, Uncertainty, Communication, Risk, Assessment, Vulnerability

1 Introduction

Uncertainty is inherent to climate information and accounting for and communicating uncertainty is therefore of paramount importance to the development and implementation of climate services. Within the Climateurope2 project, Task 4 of Work Package 2 is looking at methods and practices for uncertainty and risk assessment methods to enhance the trustworthiness of climate services in climate adaptation and the management of climate risks. For the identification of risk is the starting point for climate action.

The ultimate objective of Task 4 is to develop guidelines for gathering and propagating uncertainty assessment on the whole value chain including uncertainty communication and uncertainty assessment for risks, trends and extremes. This includes modelling strategies and methods of uncertainty quantification in climate predictions, projections and forecasts as well as uncertainties introduced in the processing of data (such as bias adjustment) and the impact assessment that often underpins climate risk analyses. The task will also explore optimal communication approaches to enhance the usability of uncertainty information and thus the understanding of it by both those providing and those using climate services.

The aim of this report is to collect examples of best practices in uncertainty quantification and communication in climate services as well as related fields. The report draws largely from existing literature and reports. Examples and best practices were also collected from the Climateurope2 community during an online workshop on communicating climate uncertainty that was held in November 2023. During the workshop, participants discussed how users of climate information deal with uncertainties and how providers of climate services should communicate about uncertainties in ways that enable users to extract the information they need.

The report is divided into two main parts, discussing the current state-of-the-art and best practices in uncertainty quantification (Chapter 2) and communication (Chapter 4). The report also looks into emerging strategies to deal with deep uncertainties that cannot be quantified (Chapter 3). It discusses a number of recent examples in practice for assessing, quantifying and communicating uncertainty in climate information (Chapter 5). Finally, the report will identify some emerging themes (Chapter 6).

1.1 Uncertainty: concepts and definitions

The word “uncertainty” means different things to different people, and in different contexts. In statistics and data science, for example, uncertainty is often used in relation to the dispersion of data points and may be quantified as variance or standard deviation. In a broader context, uncertainty is often used to refer to the unpredictability of future events and their potential impact on decision-making.

Based on earlier assessment reports, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2021) defines the concept of **uncertainty** as:

“A state of incomplete knowledge that can result from a lack of information or from disagreement about what is known or even knowable. It may have many types of sources, from imprecision in the data to ambiguously defined concepts or terminology, incomplete understanding of critical processes, or uncertain projections of human behaviour.”

Uncertainty is unavoidable in climate forecasting due to the chaotic nature of the atmosphere, the challenges of observational data (e.g. quality, length, density of network, access to metadata, and insufficient samples of extreme events) and the approximations of the forecast models (WMO, 2018).

Uncertainty may also arise through the processing of data, for example by interpolation (e.g. a statistical or physical model-based interpolation of a field between available estimates to create a more spatio-temporally complete estimate), or when estimating trends. Uncertainty may be represented by quantitative measures (e.g. a probability density function) or by qualitative statements (e.g. reflecting the judgement of a team of experts) (IPCC, 2021).

At a fundamental level, a distinction can be made between **aleatory uncertainties** that can be treated as a random variable and may be expressed in terms of probabilities, and **epistemic** or **deep uncertainties** that include concepts such as ambiguity, reliability, inconsistency and surprises which are not easily represented as probabilities (Beven et al., 2018a). The IPCC 6th Assessment Report also acknowledges the concept of **deep uncertainty** (IPCC, 2021):

A situation of deep uncertainty exists when experts or stakeholders do not know or cannot agree on: (1) appropriate conceptual models that describe relationships among key driving forces in a system; (2) the probability distributions used to represent uncertainty about key variables and parameters; and/or (3) how to weigh and value desirable alternative outcomes.

Deep uncertainty, therefore, refers to a state of incomplete knowledge and understanding that goes beyond standard (aleatory) uncertainty. It involves fundamental ambiguity about the underlying system, its dynamics, and the relevant decision-making context.

1.2 Sources of uncertainty in the climate-impact modelling chain

Uncertainty may arise in all stages of a typical climate services value chain, starting with the climate data itself. Even if the climate information is based on observations, there will be some uncertainty arising from measurement error or interpolation of point measurements to larger areas, among other sources. Uncertainties can also be related to lead time, the variable of interest, and temporal and spatial scale. (WMO, 2018).

1.2.1 Uncertainty and Time Horizons

When dealing with information about future climate change, it is common to discriminate three main sources of uncertainty: natural variability, scenario uncertainty and model uncertainty (see, e.g. Hawkins & Sutton 2009, 2011). The relative importance of these three sources is not static but depends on the time horizon of interest (Figure 1.1), the study region and the variable under consideration. Natural variability is especially important at shorter timescales (i.e. years to decades) as it may mask any longer-term changes and trends. Nonetheless, the interaction between natural climate variability and climate change can non-linearly impact uncertainty of extreme values across timescales (e.g. by modifying the tails of the distribution or the type of distribution itself).

At longer timescales, climate projections are uncertain first and foremost because we are uncertain about future levels of greenhouse gas emissions and concentrations, which in turn depend on the ambitions and implementation of climate policies, and on how human society will develop. Projections

of long-term climate change are therefore based on a set of assumptions, or scenarios, about how these factors will evolve. The sixth assessment report of the IPCC adopted five Shared Socio-economic pathways (SSPs) that examine how global society, demographics and economics might change over the next century (Riahi et al., 2017).

Uncertainty also arises from the use of models. It is common to subdivide uncertainty within the modelling process into (1) uncertainty about the model structure or, in other words, about how to represent the physics of the system; (2) uncertainty about the input data and model parameter values, which extends to the data used for model calibration and evaluation; and (3) the residual unpredictability of events for given models and parameters.

A fourth source of uncertainty is particularly relevant in seasonal to decadal climate prediction, and relates to the initial conditions, where small errors in the initial state of the model can grow into marked differences in the development of the climate system (Suckling 2018).

Data uncertainty. A measure of “noise” in the observational data that deviates from the correct, intended or original values. All measurements of an observed phenomenon have a degree of uncertainty regardless of precision and accuracy. Observational uncertainty is caused by two factors, the limitation of the measuring instrument (systematic error) and the skill of the observer making the measurements (random error). Further uncertainty can arise when, for instance, values are rounded, interpolated or extrapolated, such as when gridded analyses produce interpolated values that differ from the actual point value (WMO, 2019).

Figure 1.1: Sources of uncertainty in climate projections as a function of time horizon based on analysis of CMIP5 results, presented as a plume (a) and as a fraction of the total variance (b). (a) Projections of global mean decadal mean surface air temperature to 2100 together with a quantification of the uncertainty arising from internal variability (orange), model spread (blue) and RCP scenario spread (green). (b) Fraction of variance explained by each source of uncertainty. Note Figure (b) could be misinterpreted as showing that model spread is decreasing after the 2030s, while in fact it keeps growing throughout the century. From Chapter 11 of the IPCC WGI AR5 and Hawkins and Sutton (2009, 2011).

1.2.2 Communication through the value chain

Uncertainties do not only arise in the production of climate data and information. It is important to consider the entire value chain, which includes data processing steps such as bias correction and downscaling; impact modelling and assessment; risk evaluation; and adaptation responses (Wilby & Dessai (2010). Each component in this “cascade” will have its own associated uncertainties (Beven et al. 2018; see also Kundzewicz et al., (2018a) and Dankers & Kundzewicz (2020) for a more comprehensive discussion). Even the communication of information may add uncertainty as a recipient may not understand or interpret the climate information as intended by the producer.

Walker et al. (2010) describe a categorisation system for uncertainty which discriminates among three dimensions: **location**, **level** and **nature** of uncertainty (Figure 1.2). The *location* of the uncertainty, in this context, describes its position in the modelling pipeline (the layers of the cascade of Wilby and Dessai, 2010). The *nature* of the uncertainty describes whether the uncertainty primarily stems from knowledge imperfection (epistemic) or is a direct consequence of inherent variability (aleatory). The *level* (or degree) of uncertainty is about where uncertainty manifests itself on the gradual spectrum from determinism, through probability and possibility to ignorance (Dessai and Hulme 2003). Van Bree and Van der Sluijs (2014) expand the three-dimension model further to also include **qualification of knowledge base** and **value-ladenness of choices**. The first (qualification of knowledge base) relates to the evidence and reliability of the information used, the latter (value-ladenness of choices) to the extent to which choices made in the assessment are subjective.

Figure 1.2: Three dimensions to categorise uncertainty: location, nature, and level (degree). Modified after Walker et al. (2010), Wilby and Dessai (2010)

2 Current practices in uncertainty quantification

To ensure transparency and maintain trust in a climate service, it is essential that uncertainties are evaluated and - to the extent possible - quantified, even if they cannot be reduced. Various approaches have been developed over the years to evaluate the uncertainty in the different parts of a typical climate-impact modelling chain, many of which can also be applied in climate services. Van Bree & Van der Sluijs (2014) list a number of methods and approaches that have been used in climate change and adaptation decision making, including (in no particular order):

- Scenario analysis
- Expert elicitation
- Sensitivity analysis
- Monte Carlo simulations
- Multi-model ensemble analysis
- Bayesian methods
- Numerical Unit Spread Assessment Pedigree
- Fuzzy sets / imprecise probabilities
- Stakeholder analysis
- Quality assurance / quality checklists
- Extended peer review / review by stakeholders
- Wild cards / surprise scenarios

2.1 Uncertainty quantification in climate modelling

2.1.1 Multi-model ensemble

The standard way to evaluate climate model structural uncertainty has been through model intercomparisons, notably in the various phases of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) that have been organised since 1995. By running experiments in a standardised way, model intercomparison projects (MIPs) allow the creation of a multi-model ensemble that can be used to explore the effect of structural uncertainty in the model formulation on the simulation of a key variable, such as global mean temperature. Assuming the sample of models is large enough, the performance of the ensemble as a whole can be summarised using statistics such as the ensemble mean, which in many cases has been found to outperform any individual model when comparing with observations.

However, care must be taken when analysing the results of multi-model ensembles, as the usual statistical assumptions may not hold. Many multi-model ensembles are in fact “ensembles of opportunity” and were not designed for such a statistical analysis at the outset. A key concern is to what extent these models can be considered independent. For the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project CMIP5 ensemble of General Circulation Models (GCMs), Knutti et al. (2013) established that many GCMs were not only strongly tied to their predecessors, but also exchanged ideas and code with other models, implying that the CMIP5 models were neither independent of each other nor independent of the earlier generation.

As there are likely some overlaps in the results from the individual models, and because working with the full ensemble is often not practical - the latest CMIP6 contains results from over 100 models - various techniques have been proposed in the literature to either select a representative sample of

GCMs or to weight the results from different models differently. Model selection or weighting can be done according to a number of criteria, including:

- Realism in simulating the historical climate (i.e., model performance);
- Representativeness of the spread in future projections;
- Independence of models.

The ‘optimal’ set of models will be different for different regions and dependent on the variable or variables of interest (see e.g., McSweeney & Jones, 2016). More recently, approaches based on information theory (Pechlivanidis et al., 2018) and expert elicitation (Sebok et al., 2022) have also been proposed.

2.1.2 Perturbed-parameter ensemble

A second type of ensemble has been applied to study the effect of uncertainty in model parameters on climate impact projections. In “perturbed-parameter” ensembles (Murphy et al. 2007; Frame et al. 2009), a single GCM is run multiple times with different values for some of the key parameters. Due to computational limits, a formal sampling of the full parameter space is out of reach for state-of-the-art, complex earth system models. In practice, the key parameters and parameter values are chosen from ranges considered plausible on the basis of expert judgement. Statistical methods have also been used to estimate the set of projections that would be produced if more comprehensive sampling of parameter uncertainty in the model could be performed (see, e.g. Sexton et al. 2012). More recently methods have been proposed to pre-filter the parameter space by finding plausible candidates from a large set of cheaper, coarse-resolution atmosphere-only simulations, at the same time ensuring sufficient diversity with respect to some predefined climate change metrics (Sexton et al., 2021). The experimental setup of perturbed-parameter ensembles allows for a more formal statistical analysis of the results; however the results are usually limited to a single model only. In other words, model structural uncertainty is not accounted for. A common finding from these studies, though, is that the uncertainty range in perturbed-parameter ensembles overlaps with those of multi-model ensembles.

2.1.3 Initial condition ensemble

A third type of ensemble samples the uncertainty in the initial conditions at the start of a model run, as small errors in the initial state can grow into marked differences in the development of the climate system. Apart from numerical weather prediction, this type of ensemble modelling is used primarily at seasonal to decadal timescales, where uncertainty due to natural variability in the climate system dominates. However, initial conditions ensembles have also been used at longer timescales to explore internal variability in the model and to better evaluate changes in the likelihood of very extreme events (e.g., Maher et al., 2019). Taken at “face value”, the probability of an event may be estimated as the relative frequency of its occurrence among the ensemble members (Katz & Ehrendorfer, 2006). In practice, though, it is important to account for biases as initial condition ensembles do not sample all of the model parameters or the structural uncertainty. For this reason, seasonal forecasts are increasingly based on a multi-model evaluation as well. Moreover, it is essential to use information about the past performance of a forecasting system, typically available in the form of hindcasts to try to correct for model drift, biases and spread deficiencies and, ideally, to transform raw ensemble results into estimates that are descriptive of the true probabilities of an event (Parker, 2010). The large number of simulations that are available from hindcasts has also been used to more robustly estimate the likelihood of very extreme (and therefore rare) events (e.g., Ehmele et al., 2020; Kelder et al., 2020).

2.2 Uncertainty quantification in climate data processing

The various processing steps typically applied to climate model data, including downscaling and bias correction, also have the potential to add uncertainty to the results. For example, an implicit assumption in many bias correction techniques is that biases found in the simulation of the past climate (typically by comparing the model simulations with observations or observation-based datasets) will be similar under future - and often very different - climate conditions. Although the limitations of these assumptions underpinning most bias correction techniques (and, by extension, statistical downscaling methods) have long been recognised (e.g., Ehret et al., 2012; Maraun et al., 2017), the effect of these on the outcomes of an analysis are often not assessed. The impact of the choice of different bias correction methods has been investigated in a number of studies, particularly in hydrological applications (e.g., Chen et al., 2011, 2013; Senatore et al., 2022), although it is still not common practice. Often the contribution of the bias correction method to the overall uncertainty in the results is found to be relatively smaller than the climate model or the scenario uncertainty, but in some cases the bias correction even changed the direction of the climate signal that was present in the original climate simulations (e.g., Huang et al., 2014).

2.3 Uncertainty quantification in climate impact assessment

Similar to climate modelling, the uncertainty associated with the use of climate impact models can be evaluated through model intercomparisons, as is done in, e.g., the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP, <https://www.isimip.org/>). Comparatively fewer studies have looked at the effect of impact model parameter uncertainty, although techniques for quantifying both structural and parameter uncertainty, such as the Generalized Likelihood Uncertainty Estimation (GLUE) method (Beven & Binley, 1992) have been around for several decades. Most of these techniques rely on Monte Carlo simulations or similar approaches with the simulation results expressed as probability distributions of possible outcomes, as opposed to a single deterministic prediction.

Fewer studies still have made a thorough end-to-end assessment of the uncertainties involved in the entire climate-impact modelling chain looking at all contributing factors,, as was done for the entire flood risk chain by Metin et al. (2018) or for hydrological impacts of climate change in Nepal by Aryal et al. (2019).

While most studies adopt a “top-down” approach exploring the accumulation of uncertainty from emission scenarios to global climate response to regional or local impacts, some have also proposed a “bottom-up” approach starting from the impacted system and exploring how resilient it is to changes and variations in one or more climate variables (Van Bree & Van der Sluijs, 2014). Such a bottom-up approach is focused more on resilience of the system and how adaptation can make it less prone to uncertain and largely unpredictable changes in climate.

An example of a more bottom-up approach is the use of impact-response surfaces where an impact model is used to evaluate the response of a system across a range of conditions. Not only does this allow for a more rigorous testing of the impact models (across many possible future conditions), but it also makes it possible to identify critical impact thresholds which might be missed if only a few climate scenarios are evaluated (Fronzek et al., 2022). Examples of this approach include the scenario-neutral approach proposed by Prudhomme et al. (2010) for fluvial flood impacts in the UK; and the application of response surface diagrams for evaluating climate change impacts on crop production by Van Minnen et al. (2000). Pirttioja et al. (2019) used a similar approach to evaluate adaptation options to crop yield shortfalls under climate change.

2.4 Passing uncertainty information on down the value chain

Especially when using a top-down approach, the different processing steps in a typical climate-impact modelling chain can give rise to what has been called a “cascade of uncertainty” (Wilby & Dessai, 2010; Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: The cascade of uncertainty illustrating the potential growth of the envelope of uncertainty and the scale of the uncertainty provenance task. In practice, a bottom-up approach that begins with climate impacts will reduce the communication challenge to a set of discrete pathways (grey triangle going upwards). Modified after Wilby and Dessai (2010).

Uncertainty information is generated upstream and passed on downstream. Each step of the cascade (or value chain) will have uncertainty associated with it that needs to be passed on and sufficiently **understood** to assess its relevance to the subsequent users of the data or information.

While a climate service may need to keep a provenance record of the full depth and breadth of the cascade of uncertainty for its data holdings (figure 2.1), the specific uncertainty information to be communicated for any one study will only be that which is representative of the actual data used, and tailored to the intended audience.

Each step in the cascade or value chain represents a different community of practice, so uncertainty information may need to be understood by actors that are far removed from the original work. Metadata ontologies such as the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) (Matentzoglou et al. 2022) provide a potential framework for maintaining a shared understanding of uncertainty information throughout the value chain. SSSOM is analogous to the I-ADOPT interoperability framework for observable properties developed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) working group for Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology (Magagna et al., 2021) described in Climateurope2 Deliverable 2.1. However, SSSOM is also able to explicitly capture the imprecision, inaccuracy and incompleteness of mapped concepts.

2.4.1 Uncertainty in decision making frameworks

One of the reasons why uncertainty information needs to be passed along the value chain is that it has the potential to make a difference to the decision that is being targeted by the climate service. At the same time, an uncertainty assessment has to be appropriate to the type of the decision being made, because of the time and effort being involved (Beven et al., 2018b) and the demands of clear communication.

If the level of uncertainty can be described probabilistically, a classic risk approach (e.g., a cost-loss decision model) may be used. However, in a climate change context, this is rarely the case. The main drivers of climate change (which include economic development and population growth) are inherently uncertain, especially at the longer term, and can only be explored using a scenario approach. Moreover, at a detailed level our understanding of the Earth system is rather incomplete which may give rise to surprises, unforeseen effects and unanticipated impacts (sometimes referred to as 'ignorance'). Therefore, decision-making frameworks are needed that can cope with scenario uncertainty and ignorance. Van Bree & Van der Sluijs (2014) describe three steps to account for uncertainties in a decision framework:

1. Identify and characterise sources of uncertainty;
2. Assess (weigh, appraise, and prioritise) sources of uncertainty;
3. Select and apply methods for dealing with uncertainties.

The first step is likely to result in a long list of uncertainty sources and could be approached by analysing each step of the value chain or assessment process, or by considering where in the assessment the different types of uncertainty may occur.

In the second step, the relative importance of each uncertainty source can be evaluated by its impact on the final decision or outcome. This may be done by performing a sensitivity analysis or, if quantification is not possible, could be based on expert judgement.

In the third step, some of the key uncertainties and their impact on the final decision may be analysed and characterised in more detail. Van Bree & Van der Sluijs (2014) highlight that the uncertainties will need to be re-evaluated throughout the assessment process, as it may not be possible to identify, prioritise and characterise all sources of uncertainty right at the start.

To be useful in a decision-making process, the uncertainties obviously need not only to be analysed and described, but also communicated to the decision- or policy-maker. It is therefore important to evaluate which uncertainties are most relevant for the decision at hand, and - if relevant - identify options that are robust given these uncertainties (Van Bree & Van der Sluijs, 2014). The way that information is presented can also have an impact on its interpretation and the decisions that are made on the basis of it. To avoid misinterpretation, decision makers should be provided with a fuller understanding of the context of the information that is given to them, yet not so much information that it would overload them. For instance, to limit the overload potential it can be useful to have a range of methods with which to communicate uncertainty and then to use those methods that are most relevant to the situation.

The World Meteorological Organisation (2011) identifies a need for capacity development of both the users and providers of climate services to build the necessary understanding, confidence and skills to quantify and utilize probability and uncertainty better to support decisions and actions.

Some practical examples of how uncertainty information is used to inform climate adaptation decisions can be found in Lourenço et al. (2014).

2.4.2 Example of passing uncertainty information on through the value chain

An example of how quantitative uncertainty information can be used in decision-making is provided in this section.

Technical products provided today by National Meteorological Services and related institutes mainly involve forecasts of precipitation and mean, maximum and minimum temperature. These products lead in general to different managerial actions for different sectors, and therefore stakeholders normally need to go one step further in order to use them for their specific interests, for a hazard only becomes a risk if there is a vulnerability to it.

Therefore a hazard-oriented approach alone, which prioritises the sources of harm, is not enough because of its lack of information on the local sensitivity, exposure and adaptive capacity of the population. An adequate, comprehensive approach requires risk assessment, involving the difficult problem of satisfactorily quantifying both hazards and vulnerabilities for the specific sector (e.g. water availability, agriculture, health or energy managements), region of the world, and time scale (e.g. short-term, intraseasonal, seasonal, decadal, long-term) of interest (e.g. Muñoz et al. 2012). Unfortunately, due to the complicated character of the addressed problem, there is no unique methodology to quantify the risk, and different approaches are employed for different activities.

These issues make it extremely difficult to compare risk indices on different regions of the world, or even among different sectors (e.g. agriculture and health) for the same geographical region. Moreover, in the cases where risk estimations are available, they tend to exclude information on the associated uncertainties.

A way to circumvent these problems is to use a *probabilistic risk management* approach (e.g. Mora and Keipi, 2006; Mora, 2009; Muñoz et al., 2012), which permits to operationally define a probabilistic vulnerability distribution that is by construction consistent with both the hazard and risk probability density functions. At its core, this approach directly identifies risk with key indicators for decision makers, such as damage or cost, for which real data exists, and from which an empirical (or fitted) probability distribution can be obtained.

To illustrate the case with a real-world example, consider the annual, total maize yield production (in hectograms by hectare, Hg/Ha) for Guatemala, from 1961 to 2005 (Figure 2.2). The maize yield can be translated into damage cost, for example in hundred of thousands US\$, and a probability density function describing the probability distribution can be directly defined from the data record. For the sake of simplicity, assume that such a distribution follows a Gaussian distribution (as in the Figure 2.2) –nonetheless the distribution does not need to be a Gaussian one. In that case, a natural measure of uncertainty is provided by the dispersion parameter of the distribution, or the standard deviation in this case.

A similar approach can be followed for the hazard, which in the example of Figure 2.2 is measured via the Palmer Drought Standardised Index (PDSI), which also conveys information on the related uncertainties via the corresponding probability distribution (see example in Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Illustration on how to define the risk and hazard probability density functions and related definitions of risk, using real maize yield data for Guatemala (green time series curve). In this example, the key hazard is related to droughts, as measured by the Palmer Drought Standardised Index (PDSI, blue time series curve).

As suggested by Muñoz et al (2012), it is obvious that, given that the probability density functions for the risk and the hazard are known, a risk manager can mathematically define the associated vulnerability's probability density function that is consistent with both the risk and the hazard ones. Furthermore, it is possible to then define which vulnerability distribution is required to obtain a risk distribution that the decision makers can cope with, i.e. a re-engineering of the vulnerability distribution given the knowledge of the present and future hazard distribution, and considering the desired or manageable risk distribution (Muñoz et al., 2012). For example, the risk manager might want to have a distribution that provides the most part of the probability distribution that corresponds to low values of risk. A possible choice for such a probability distribution is the exponential distribution (on the left panel of Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Conceptual example illustrating the re-engineering of vulnerabilities and management of the related uncertainties.

Overall, the approach enables decision makers not only to quantitatively assess risk and the related uncertainties, but also to support the choice of strategies and tasks that will help achieve a certain desired vulnerability distribution (that translates into concrete exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacities for the population).

2.5 Uncertainties in extremes

Key climate risks are often (though not always) associated with the occurrence of extreme events. Evaluating the nature and probability of these extremes including the possible effect of climate change is, however, subject to considerable uncertainty above and beyond the sources of uncertainty already discussed earlier in this report. Even the word “extreme” is in itself ambiguous, as there is no standard definition of when an event can be considered extreme. Some studies of climate extremes focus on the upper end of the distribution of a climate variable, for example the 90th percentile of daily maximum temperature, or the 95th or 99th percentile of daily rainfall (e.g., Donat et al., 2013; Contractor et al., 2021), which - depending on the precise definition - may be expected to be exceeded every year, if not multiple times per year (Myhre et al., 2019). Others focus on events that are much rarer: studies of changes in river flood frequency, for example, often use river flows with an annual probability of exceedance of 1% (average return period of 100 years, or a “once-in-100-years” flood), although return periods of 10 or 30 years have also been used (Kundzewicz et al., 2018b). The IPCC (2021) defines a climate extreme as *“the occurrence of a value of a weather or climate variable above (or below) a threshold value near the upper (or lower) ends of the range of observed values of the variable. By definition, the characteristics of what is called extreme weather may vary from place to place in an absolute sense.”*

A key challenge in the estimation of especially high-impact extreme events to which society is not well adapted or prepared, such as severe flooding or intensive heatwaves, is that such events are typically very rare. This means that the sample size of these events - to study their nature and impacts, let alone perform a statistical analysis or detect any trends - can be very small or even non-existent. Take, for

example, the “once-in-a-100 years” flood event, or more precisely the river flow level with an annual probability of exceedance of 1%, which in many countries serves as a baseline for flood protection measures. The probability of exceeding this level at least once in a 100-year time series of data (observations or model-based) *at the same location* is only about 63%, meaning there is still a chance of 37% of not observing this river flow level at all. However, to detect a trend you would ideally need multiple events, and the probability of exceeding the 100-year flood level at least three times in a century is - statistically speaking - only about 8% (Cloke & Pappenberger, 2009). In reality, the statistical distribution is unlikely to remain stationary over such extended periods, not only due to climate variability and long-term climate change, but also because of land use change, changes in water management practices, engineering interventions, and other anthropogenic and environmental factors. In addition there may be inhomogeneities in the data, for example due to changes to the observation network, changes in the measurement method, or instrument drift. Measurements of extreme events can also be uncertain as instruments sometimes break down or wash away, or have been calibrated under different conditions. River flow, for example, is typically observed by measuring water level; the relationship between water height and flow volume (the rating curve) that is established during “normal” flow conditions may, however, no longer be valid during a flood (Di Baldassarre & Montanari, 2009; Hamilton & Moore, 2013).

Because of the often limited sample size, the probability or frequency of extreme events is often estimated by fitting an extreme value distribution to a larger sample of the data, such as the annual maximum (or minimum) values or all peak values over a predefined threshold. Although these distributions provide a more robust estimate of extreme quantiles, these are nevertheless increasingly uncertain at more extreme levels, especially if the return period exceeds the length of the data record. Also the choice of the extreme value distribution (e.g., Generalised Extreme Value (GEV) vs. Gumbel) can bias return period estimates, as can the use of stationary models when the underlying distribution is changing due to climate or land use changes. Conversely, modelling non-stationarity introduces additional structural uncertainty in the estimates.

Uncertainty in the evaluation of climate extremes may also arise from the communication and interpretation of some of the key concepts. A common source of misunderstanding is related to the concept of return period as reflected in phrases such as “a once-in-a-100-years” event or in short a “100-year event”. Statistically, such an event has an annual probability of exceedance of 1% which (in theory at least) applies *every year*, regardless of whether a similar event has just happened or not. The *average* recurrence interval between two events then works out as 100 years only when averaging over many events; statistically it is very well possible for multiple “100-year” events to happen within a relatively short timespan. However, many people interpret the concept of a 100-year event as an event that happens exactly once every 100 years, resulting in misunderstandings such as thinking that a new event is less likely when one has just occurred, or more likely when it has not happened for a long time (the “flood is due” effect; Grounds et al., 2018). Such misinterpretation of technical terms can result in a misperception of risk and ultimately negatively affect decision-making, for example around insurance or preparedness (Lee et al., 2021). But also other technical concepts related to the communication of uncertainty such as ranges, probabilities, and confidence levels can be misunderstood or underutilised by stakeholders.

2.5.1 Strategies for dealing with uncertainties in extremes

Methods for evaluating and/or quantifying the uncertainty in climate extremes are to some extent similar to those discussed earlier in this chapter for climate data in general. For example, it is advisable to adopt a multi-model and multi-scenario approach to investigate the influence of scenario and model structural uncertainty on the outcomes, including the effects of impact model uncertainty

where appropriate. If statistical models are being used to estimate the likelihood of extremes, multiple extreme value distributions (e.g., GEV, Gumbel, Generalised Pareto) could be applied to test the robustness of the results. Likewise, covariates can be included into the extreme value distributions when this is justified (Coles, 2001; Katz et al., 2002). Methods also exist to calculate the parameter uncertainty in these distributions explicitly using bootstrapping or Bayesian inference (e.g., Gilleland, 2020; Cindrić & Pasarić, 2019).

If the sample of extreme events is too small and/or too much affected by natural variability, a more robust signal of changes in extremes may sometimes be obtained by aggregating over larger regions. This has been found for climate variables such as precipitation (Fischer et al., 2013) but also may also apply to timeseries of flood events (Dankers & Kundzewicz, 2020). Large initial-condition climate model ensembles or millennial scale climate simulations provide an opportunity to estimate the role of natural variability in extreme-event probability giving more robust estimates (e.g., Huang et al., 2016; Maher et al., 2021). The he UNSEEN method (UNprecedented Simulated Extremes using ENsembles; Thompson et al., 2017) extends this approach to large ensembles of past seasonal or decadal forecast or hindcast data to identify plausible—but previously unseen—extreme weather events by sampling well beyond the observational record, and has been used by, e.g., Kay et al. (2024) to estimate the likelihood of unprecedented hydrological extremes that lie outside the range of historical observations.

2.6 Uncertainty evaluation across timescales

Different sources of uncertainty dominate at different time horizons, and the approaches used to quantify or manage them vary accordingly. Table 2.1 provides a structured overview of the main sources of uncertainty—ranging from observational and modelling limitations to internal climate variability and scenario uncertainty—across the typical timescales of climate information (historical observations, seasonal prediction, decadal prediction, and long-term projections). The table also outlines common strategies to address these uncertainties, drawing on established practices in the climate science literature (e.g., Hawkins & Sutton 2009; IPCC, 2021; Doblas-Reyes et al. 2013; Meehl et al., 2014).

Table 2.1: Overview of the main sources of uncertainty in climate data across timescales, plus strategies for evaluating the uncertainty. Based on established practices in the climate science literature (e.g., Hawkins & Sutton 2009; IPCC, 2021; Doblas-Reyes et al. 2013; Meehl et al., 2014).

Time scale	Main sources of uncertainty	Strategies
Historical climate (observations, reanalyses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement errors (instrument calibration, homogenization issues) • Changes in station locations/methods • Incomplete spatial coverage • Reanalysis model dependence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigorous quality control and homogenization • Use of multiple observational datasets (gauge, satellite, reanalysis) • Metadata and bias corrections • Data rescue & paleoclimate proxies for extension
Seasonal prediction (months to ~1 year)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model structural uncertainty (initialisation, physics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use multi-model ensembles (e.g., C3S, NMME) • Ensemble initialisations to

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal variability (ENSO, MJO, NAO etc.) ● Limited predictability horizon ● Initial and boundary condition uncertainty (SSTs, soil moisture, sea ice) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● sample internal variability ● Hindcast-based calibration and bias correction ● Probabilistic forecast products
Decadal prediction (1–10 years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal climate variability (decadal oscillations, volcanic eruptions) ● Model drift and bias ● Initial condition data ● Moderate scenario uncertainty (esp. aerosols, near-term emissions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initialised decadal prediction ensembles ● Multi-model comparisons ● Bias adjustment & drift correction ● Large ensembles to separate forced signal from variability
Long-term climate projections (multi-decadal to century)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Emission/scenario uncertainty (dominant beyond ~2050) ● Climate model structural uncertainty ● Internal variability (more important at regional scales) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use of multiple emission scenarios (SSPs/RCPs) ● Multi-model ensembles (CMIP, CORDEX) ● Large initial-condition ensembles for variability quantification ● Storyline approaches for communicating divergent outcomes

3 Strategies for deep uncertainties

3.1 Understanding deep uncertainty

When a system is well understood and there are good measurements available, then uncertainty can be presented using statistical methods and probabilities as is commonly the case for weather forecasts. Uncertainties associated with limited knowledge, for example about future socio-economic and technological developments and about certain aspects of the climate system, are more appropriately conveyed with the use of scenarios that indicate “what if” situations.

Figure 3.1 Continuum of uncertainty. The realm of probabilities and other methods to represent uncertainty when comparing the knowledge about outcomes with the knowledge about likelihoods. Modified after Dessai and Hulme (2003), Stirling (1998).

Epistemic or deep uncertainty refers to a state of incomplete knowledge and understanding that goes beyond standard uncertainty. It involves fundamental ambiguity about the underlying system, its dynamics, and the relevant decision-making context. This concept is related to the notion of “vague uncertainties” of Budescu and Wallsten (1987) and similar concepts dating back to at least the 1920s. Deep uncertainty is often characterised by the inability to assign precise probabilities to future events or to fully comprehend the system's complexity. It often involves unknown unknowns, where potential future scenarios and their likelihoods are difficult to define.

Deep uncertainty challenges traditional decision-making frameworks that assume a known and probabilistic future, requiring approaches that can navigate ambiguity, embrace scenario thinking, and incorporate adaptive strategies to account for the inherent unpredictability of certain situations. It also has implications for communication as overly precise numerical expressions of the likelihood of a particular event or outcome are potentially misleading.

3.2 Accounting for deep uncertainty

A common approach to navigating and dealing with deep uncertainty is employing scenarios. Scenarios involve the creation of plausible and divergent narratives or storylines that outline different potential futures. By exploring a range of scenarios, decision-makers can better understand the spectrum of possible outcomes and prepare adaptive strategies that are robust across various eventualities.

There is no single way of establishing the impact of deep uncertainty on the outcomes of a risk analysis in a more quantitative sense, although methods have been proposed that allow combining probability distributions with measures of belief and disbelief, such as the Dempster-Shafer method or subjective logic.

Beven et al. (2018a) suggested that good practice requires that assumptions that have been made during the analysis about the sources and nature of uncertainties are recorded and communicated to the users. For robust decision making, it will be important to examine the sensitivity of the decisions to alternative assumptions that could have been made, to communicate the meaning of the associated uncertainty estimates, and to provide an audit trail of the analysis (Beven et al., 2018b).

A formal elaboration of this idea can be found in a recommended practice for assurance of simulation modes that was compiled by the accredited registrar and classification society DNV (2021). By combining information about the uncertainty associated with the model with an assessment on the consequences of a possible wrong decision that the model is supporting, the risk associated with the use of the model on the outcome can be evaluated (Figure 3.2). The categorisation of the consequences obviously depends on the context and may need to be coordinated with the user, for example for safety issues a minor could mean “one or more minor injuries” and catastrophic “multiple fatalities.”

	Severity of consequence if function does not work as intended			
	Minor	Significant	Severe	Catastrophic
High uncertainty that model does not represent relevant aspects of the reality	2	3	4	Not Trusted
Medium uncertainty that model does not represent relevant aspects of the reality	1	2	3	4
Low uncertainty that model does not represent relevant aspects of the reality	0	1	2	3

Figure 3.2: Risk matrix combining a categorisation of the uncertainty associated with the use of a particular model with a categorisation of the consequences. Source: DNV (2021).

DNV also recommends using uncertainty shaping factor checklists to understand and classify uncertainty (the vertical axis in the matrix; DNV, 2021). Such checklists could be adapted for use in climate services.

Identifying and evaluating the effect of the assumptions that have been made as part of the process is therefore an important part of any risk assessment, yet it can be challenging as many assumptions are tacit and not explicit. People involved in the process may not even know that they have made assumptions, yet the assumptions have the potential to obscure a major part of the risk.

Assumptions occur at each step of the risk assessment process, from defining the scope, to selecting a workflow within that scope, to summarising the results with metrics. An awareness of where assumptions can occur and a systematic way of checking whether assumptions have been made can be very insightful.

One way to assess how critical assumptions are is through a method called assumption-deviation risk. Flage (2019) provides a framework for quantifying the criticality of a risk assessment’s assumptions based on the consequences of a deviation from the assumption along three components (Table 3.1): the sensitivity of the conclusion with respect to the assumption; the strength of knowledge (SoK) supporting the assumption; and the belief in the possibility of deviations or even violations of the assumption.

An assumption with low criticality (setting I) can be considered reliable because there is little expectation that it may not be true, it has little impact on the conclusion of the assessment and the strength of knowledge that supports it is strong. Whereas risk assessment metrics based on assumptions with high criticality (settings V and VI) should be treated with caution.

Table 3.1: Quantification of the criticality of assumptions to risk assessment metrics, after Flage (2019).

Belief in deviation	Sensitivity of risk metric with respect to assumption deviation	SoK label	
		Strong	Moderate/ Weak
Low	Low	Setting I	Setting II
	Moderate/High	Setting III	Setting IV
Moderate/ High	Low	Setting V	Setting VI
	Moderate/High		

4 Best practices in communicating uncertainties

Communication of (future) climate information can be considered broadly equivalent to the communication of risk, especially if the impacts are considered as well. In its simplest form, communication can be viewed as the process of sending information or content (such as a message in natural language) in some form (e.g., as spoken language) from a sender or source to a receiver. This basic model of communication was first formulated by Shannon (1948) and has a long-standing history in risk communication and other disciplines, but it has also been criticised as it does not allow for, for example, differing purposes or interpretations.

More recently, risk communication is seen as an interactive exchange rather than a one-way transfer of information, knowledge and opinions. Höppner et al. (2010) identified five key elements of risk communication: actors, purposes, modes and channels, tools and the message itself. As a universal principle, the language and terms used have to fit the audience rather than the other way round: an expression such as '100-year flood' may be interpreted differently by experts and laypeople. The content and the mode of communication has to fit the needs of the audience and the requirements of the situation. To increase the credibility of the message it is important to be transparent and acknowledge uncertainty. In other words, the content should not only be about what is known, but also about the uncertainties and what is unknown. However, in order not to overwhelm the user, the uncertainty information needs to be tailored to the audience and the mode of communication.

There are many guidelines for risk communication from diverse fields such as health, food safety, and technological and chemical risks. Some practical advice for communicating climate information more broadly is given in the *The Uncertainty Handbook* (Corner et al., 2015). Although some of the 12 principles in the Handbook are aimed more at dealing with climate sceptics, many of the principles could also be applied in a climate services context:

1. Manage your audience's expectations
2. Start with what you know, not what you don't know
3. Be clear about the scientific consensus
4. Shift from 'uncertainty' to 'risk'
5. Be clear what type of uncertainty you are talking about
6. Understand what is driving people's views about climate change
7. The most important question for climate impacts is 'when', not 'if'
8. Communicate through images and stories
9. Highlight the 'positives' of uncertainty
10. Communicate effectively about climate impacts
11. Have a conversation, not an argument
12. Tell a human story, not a scientific one

4.1 Formats for communicating uncertainty

In text

Uncertainty can be conveyed in different ways, ranging from percentage probabilities and expressions of uncertainty to expressions of confidence and ambiguity, and indications of alternative scenarios (Morss et al., 2008; Van Bree & Van der Sluijs, 2014). Probabilistic predictions in particular can be communicated using precise numerical probabilities (for example, there is a 0.4 chance that X will occur), imprecise numerical probabilities (for example, the probability that X will occur is between 0.3 and 0.6) or probability phrases (for example, it is improbable that X will occur). (Budescu et al., 2014).

While it is preferable to communicate probability with precision, it's crucial to recognise that overly precise numerical expressions of likelihood can be misleading. People interpret and act on probability information differently, and decisions may be different when uncertainty information is vague rather than precise (Budescu and Wallsten, 1987). Spiegelhalter and Riesch (2011) suggest tailoring the expression of uncertainty to the depth of uncertainty; if doubts exist about the model's adequacy, resulting probabilities should not be overly precise, and a range may be more appropriate. Deeper uncertainties may be communicated by expressing confidence in the model based on quality of the evidence and/or a judgement about the robustness of the analysis. However, caution is needed in conveying complex or ambiguous information, as some individuals, especially those with low numeracy or optimism, may become confused or risk-averse (Spiegelhalter et al., 2011). This underscores the importance of understanding how target audiences interpret and use the information (Morss et al., 2008).

Table 4.1: Verbal descriptions of quantified uncertainty (or likelihood) in the guidance note for the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (Mastrandrea et al., 2011). Note phrases 'More likely than not' (for probabilities above 50%), 'Extremely likely' (for probabilities above 95%) and 'Extremely unlikely' (for probabilities below 5%) have also been used.

Description	Likelihood of the Outcome
Virtually certain	99-100%
Very likely	90-100%
Likely	66-100%
About as likely as not	33-66%
Unlikely	0-33%
Very unlikely	0-10%
Exceptionally unlikely	0-1%

Since its Fifth Assessment Report, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has used a calibrated language of verbal descriptions of quantified uncertainty (termed likelihood) (Table 4.1) to convey imprecision in its predictions and conclusions. Here likelihood may be based on statistical or modelling analyses, elicitation of expert views, or other quantitative analyses (Mastrandrea et al., 2011). However, studies have shown that these likelihood statements are often misinterpreted by laypeople, and assumed to be closer to 50% than intended. Supplementing the verbal descriptions with numerical ranges improves the understanding and leads to a better differentiation of the terms in Table 4.1 (Budescu et al., 2014).

Visualisation

Visualisations are a powerful way to communicate information and graphics are widely used in communicating climate information. However, as with verbal descriptions, visual information may be interpreted differently by experts and laypeople. When not appropriately designed and disseminated, visualisations could be confusing or misinterpreted and lead to decisions that are not well-informed.

A key principle in visual communication is that graphs and maps need to be clear and almost self-explanatory to the intended audience. This is a challenge for the visualisation of uncertainty information, which often requires some additional explanation. Especially “deeper” epistemic uncertainties are not easily presented as visualisations. Beven et al. (2018b) point out that the visualisation itself may also introduce further uncertainties, for example as a consequence of a particular interpolation or smoothing method that has been applied, or because the user may not interpret the graphical information as intended. Visualisations that are made too precise or detailed, for example, may induce an undue belief in the model performance that is not warranted by the uncertainty in the result (Beven et al., 2018b).

While the simplest way to display uncertainty information in a map is perhaps to show two maps side by side, with one map showing the actual values and the other a measure of uncertainty (such as the standard deviation or signal-to-noise ratio). As Kaye et al. (2012) point out, this approach has the obvious disadvantage that it can be problematic to read both value and uncertainty simultaneously, as mentally overlaying maps is difficult. Kaye et al. (2012) proposed a number of guidelines for representing both magnitude and uncertainty in mapping climate data. These include:

- use a sensible sequential or diverging colour scheme;
- use appropriate colour symbolism if it is applicable;
- ensure the map is accessible to everyone, including for example colour blind people;
- use a data classification scheme that does not misrepresent the data;
- use a map projection that does not distort the data;
- attempt to be visually intuitive to understand.

Kaye et al. (2012) illustrated their approach by using a bivariate technique that adjusts the hue of a small palette of colours to show the mean or median of a variable and the saturation of the colour to indicate a measure of uncertainty in this value. However, as Daron et al. (2015) point out, there is still limited empirical evidence of how different individuals and groups interpret different visualisations of climate data, potentially leading to misinterpretations. It is important to be aware that, by translating data into information and by using different visualisation styles and techniques tailored towards a specific user community, inherently a layer of interpretation is being added (Daron et al., 2015). Collecting empirical evidence on how the audiences from diverse backgrounds interpret climate visualisations is, however, not a widely adopted practice.

Storytelling

Recently, storytelling has received an increasing amount of attention as a means to communicate climate information to a non-technical audience. Telling a story means presenting information in a narrative format, offering a way of building more sustainable and meaningful engagement because people are more used to communicating information through stories than graphs and numbers (Corner et al., 2018). Not only does the use of narratives help audiences understand complex and abstract science issues, but it also makes them easier to remember and to process relative to traditional forms of scientific communication.

Shepherd et al. (2018) argue that a storyline approach may be an effective way of communicating uncertainty in the physical aspects of climate change. They define a storyline as a physically self-consistent unfolding of past events, or of plausible future events or pathways. The emphasis of a storyline is on a qualitative understanding rather than quantitative precision. No a priori probability is assigned to a particular storyline; instead, the emphasis is placed on understanding the driving factors involved and the plausibility of high-impact events.

Shepherd et al. (2018) identify four benefits of using a storyline approach. Storylines can enhance risk awareness by framing risks in an event-oriented way, aligning with how people perceive and respond to risk. A storyline approach can also strengthen decision-making by allowing backward planning from specific vulnerabilities, incorporating climate data with other factors to address compound risks. Additionally, storylines provide a physical basis for managing uncertainty, enabling the use of credible regional models. Lastly, they help explore plausible boundaries, preventing false precision and surprises. Storylines also offer the opportunity to link the physical and human aspects of climate change. In short, when co-developed by scientists and stakeholders, event-based storylines can provide a useful way of communicating and assessing climate-related risk and feed directly into a specific decision-making context (Sillmann et al., 2021). In addition, Barclay et al. (2023) demonstrate there may also be benefits to the “storyteller” themselves, as it may help rationalising their understanding and experiencing of complex, uncertain situations.

5 Examples of uncertainty assessment and communication

The previous sections summarise what the literature has to offer on communicating uncertainties in climate information. We also wanted to gather some information about if and how these methods are used in practice. In this section we will present a number of examples of how the concept, methods and practices with regards to the evaluation and communication of uncertainty are implemented by the climate services community. With the exception of the first case study, the examples were collected from the Climateurope2 community during an online workshop on communicating climate uncertainty that was held in November 2023. In total, 83 people participated in the workshop. Three lectures were given by representatives from KNMI, DNV and the Red Cross / Red Crescent. During the workshop, participants discussed how users of climate information deal with uncertainties and how providers of climate services should communicate about uncertainties in ways that enable users to extract the information they need. Below, we introduce the uncertainty communication framework used by the IPCC and summarise the inputs from the three workshop lectures.

5.1 IPCC AR6

The IPCC framework for characterising knowledge and uncertainties (Mach et al. 2017) is a single framework (Figure 5.1) that could be applied consistently across working groups, spanning diverse disciplines and topics. This shared framework aimed to increase the comparability of assessment conclusions across all topics related to climate change, from the physical science basis to resulting impacts, risks, and options for response.

The diagram in figure 5.1 illustrates the process IPCC AR6 authors used to evaluate and communicate the state of knowledge in their assessment. The process begins with evaluation of evidence and agreement (steps 1–3). Where possible, authors then evaluate confidence, synthesising evidence and agreement in one qualitative metric (steps 3–5). Where uncertainties can be quantified probabilistically, authors subsequently evaluate likelihood or a more precise measure of probability (steps 5–6). Note that the likelihood categories should be considered to have “fuzzy” boundaries (step 6 (CCSP, 2009)). Unless otherwise specified, assessment conclusions characterised probabilistically are underpinned by high or very high confidence. Authors present evidence/agreement, confidence, or likelihood terms with assessment conclusions, communicating their expert judgments accordingly. Example conclusions drawn from the IPCC AR6 are presented in the box at the bottom of the figure. (Mach et al. 2017)

Evaluation and communication of degree of certainty in AR6 findings

Figure 5.1: The IPCC AR6 approach for characterising understanding and uncertainty in assessment findings. The diagram illustrates the step-by-step process authors use to evaluate and communicate the state of knowledge in their assessment (Mastrandrea et al., 2010). Figure adapted from Mach et al. (2017).

5.2 National climate scenarios: KNMI'23

The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut - KNMI) is a national knowledge institute for weather, climate and seismology. The KNMI'23 climate scenarios (KNMI, 2023) are four new scenarios which outline what the future climate in The Netherlands could look like. With the new climate scenarios, KNMI offers guidelines for policy advisers and other professionals so they can make adequate decisions to ensure a safe, liveable and prosperous Netherlands in a changing climate. Janette Bessembinder from KNMI kindly shared with us the benefit of her experience of communicating climate information and uncertainty to wider society at the Communicating Climate Uncertainty workshop held by Climateurope2¹.

¹ <https://climateurope2.eu/news-events/events/events/communicating-climate-uncertainty>

Establish the idea of uncertainty

The first step is to establish the idea that there is not just one prediction for the future of the climate. KNMI'23 does this by presenting information in terms of two scenarios, one associated with high CO2 emissions and another with low CO2 emissions. The simple act of presenting two possible futures conveys the concept that the future is not known (is uncertain) and, more subtly, that in the long-term, the main source of that uncertainty is uncertainty associated with how humans will collectively behave.

Present an even number of climate projections

Climate communication practitioners should be aware of the impact of visual information. An audience will often interpret the middle or central projection of future climate as being the most likely when in fact no likelihood can be attributed. To avoid this bias, practitioners can present the audience with an even number of projections. Giving an even number of projections implicitly encourages the audience to think about which of the projections is the most relevant for their topic of interest.

Consider the most relevant climate risks

Climate communication practitioners should consider which are the most important climate risks for a specific audience. In The Netherlands there are distinct risks associated with dry years and with wet years, and sea-level rise is also a major concern. The most probable risks are often not the most relevant risks, so the simulated scenarios that inform an analysis should be those that do the best job at representing the risk situation that is of particular concern.

KNMI'23 uses a four quadrant framework of high emissions vs low emissions (representing uncertainty about future socio-economic and technological developments) and drier climate vs wetter climate (representing uncertainty about the climate system). The framework is used to convey an indication of the severity of climate risk factors for temperature change, wetter winters, extreme summer showers, drought, and sea-level rise. (figure 5.2)

This four quadrant format is able to convey whether year on year variability of a climate risk is to be expected. The severity of risk factors to do with temperature change and sea-level rise are only dependent on the emissions scenario. The severity of risk factors to do with wetter winters, extreme summer showers, and increased droughts are also dependent on whether the year is particularly wet or particularly dry.

The four quadrant framework adopted by KNMI presents climate uncertainty in terms of a set of threats for which to be prepared. The assumption being that information about threats which are specific and relevant for an audience empower climate action.

Figure 5.2: The four KNMI'23 scenarios for climate change in the Netherlands. The number of small blocks represents the extent of climate change around 2100 compared to 1991-2020. The four quadrant framework conveys the severity of climate risk factors associated with low and high CO₂ emissions and wetter or drier climate. KNMI (2023).

Include the lived experience of the audience

For many people, the year-to-year variability of the climate system is more important and impactful than the slow shift of long-term climate means. Information about a projected future can be made more tangible and less abstract when it is framed in the context of the lived experience of the audience.

Including year-to-year historical variability on graphs of historical and projected climate trends gives the audience an appreciation of what the variability they have experienced looks like in the context of the information that is presented about the future. For time series plots, this could be the use of 90% shading to show both the variability of the past climate as well as that of a projected future, with data for the year-to-year variability of the historical period overlaid (as in figure 5.3a). For box plots this could be overlaying the historical statistics with annual data points (as in figure 5.3b).

Presenting historical data using the same method as data for the projected future, with context via a representation of year-to-year variability, makes the information on the graph easier to understand.

Figure 5.3: Examples of making climate graphs easier to understand by using the same method to present both historical data and data for future projections, and providing context via a representation of the year-to-year variability of the historical period. a) Time-series of historical and projected summer temperature for the Netherlands (KNMI, 2023). b) The annual number of tropical days (observed and projected) for the Netherlands.

Using maps

An effective way to convey the geographical distribution of how the behaviour of a climatological index might be expected to change in the future is with a contour map. However, if the communication only provides one future instance it would convey an implicit bias towards the chosen scenario. The uncertainty of the future climate can be conveyed by showing at least two instances from different scenarios.

People like to have access to climate information that is local to them. When presenting local information, it can be better to convey the values of climate indicators in terms of their absolute values rather than as percentage changes. There is an implicit assumption that data presented as a percentage change is true for the whole of an area rather than being specific to a locality.

The language of uncertainty

Much of the language that we use as climate scientists can have a very different meaning in public life, this is particularly pertinent for the topic of uncertainty communication. It can be better to use commonly understood descriptive language in place of scientific terminology. For instance, rather than using the word “uncertainty” which implies ignorance, a better choice could be the word “range”. But if the word uncertainty can not be avoided then it should be clearly explained. More examples of commonly misunderstood climate science terminology can be found in table 5.1 .

Emphasising uncertainties too much may leave people “paralysed” and unsure of how to act. In climate change communication it is better to focus on what is known first. e.g. “all climate scenarios show that temperatures and extreme precipitation increase, even though there are some uncertainties”, rather than “there are many uncertainties about climate change, but we know that temperatures will change”. However, we should not obscure uncertainties.

Table 5.1: Examples of climate science terminology that have the potential to be misunderstood by the public and alternative options.

Terms that have different meanings for scientists and the public		
Scientific term	Public meaning	Better choice
enhance	improve	intensify, increase
aerosol	spray can	tiny atmospheric particle
positive trend	good trend	upward trend
positive feedback	good response, praise	vicious cycle, self-reinforcing cycle
theory	hunch, speculation	scientific understanding
uncertainty	ignorance	range
error	mistake, wrong, incorrect	difference from exact true number
bias	distortion, political motive	offset from an observation
sign	indication, astrological sign	plus or minus sign
values	ethics, monetary value	numbers, quantity
manipulation	illicit tampering	scientific data processing
scheme	devious plot	systematic plan
anomaly	abnormal occurrence	change from long-term average

5.3 Risk assessment: DNV

DNV² are experts in assurance (protection against events) and risk management for industry with a stated purpose to safeguard life, property and the environment. Andreas Hafver from DNV kindly gave us the benefit of his insights on risk management from an industry perspective and its relationship to uncertainty at the Communicating Climate Uncertainty workshop held by Climateurope2.

Uncertainty is a part of the risk and should not be used to take risk less seriously. In fact more uncertainty is a reason to take a risk more seriously. However, people don't like to hear about uncertainties, they want to have numbers and clear recommendations. Nevertheless, we should harness the power of uncertainty, because with an awareness of uncertainties comes an ability to assess risks more critically. More confidence can be placed in assessments of risk that are clear, in spite of the uncertainties.

Understanding Risk

There are many definitions for risk, a few examples are listed below:

- Cambridge Dictionary: “the possibility of something bad happening”
- IPCC AR6: “the potential for adverse consequences”
- ISO 31000: “the effect of uncertainty on objectives”
- ISO/IEC 61508: “combination of the probability of occurrence of harm and the severity of that harm”

In general, the principle of risk is an assessment of the likelihood (degree of certainty) about a set of consequences that are either wanted or unwanted.

² <https://www.dnv.com/about/index.html#>

A risk can be described in terms of a two axis framing of its consequences. Some consequences are wanted while others are unwanted, and some consequences are certain while others are uncertain.

The severity of the consequences of a risk will be assessed differently by different stakeholders who will have different objectives, different knowledge and different ways of knowing. The values and objectives of a society will also change through time and things that were previously not considered as risks become important to consider and vice versa.

Risk metrics and assumptions

Risk assessments often communicate risk with plots showing quantitative risk metrics (Figure 5.4). For example, risk matrices of severity and likelihood, risk maps showing the geographical distribution of risk, risk radars which show how a range of scenarios score on different parameters, exceedance curves that show the frequency of events and their impact, and forecasts of some quantity of interest with some uncertainty around the predictions with maybe a critical limit to show uncertainty about when the limit will be reached.

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Figure 5.4: Examples of quantitative metrics for communicating risk.

However, risk is more than what we can quantify with metrics. Any risk assessment involves choices and assumptions as part of the analysis. The metrics presented to describe a risk will only capture aspects of the full risk picture. Tacit assumptions made as part of the risk assessment process have the potential to obscure a major part of the risk picture. To convey a more complete picture of the risk, quantitative metrics could be accompanied by an evaluation which includes: the rationale for the metric; properties of the evidence used; degree of consensus; criticality of the assumptions; and the location, nature and degree of uncertainty (see sections 1.2 and 3).

Figure 5.5: Quantitative metrics presented to summarise an assessment of risk are only part of the full picture. An evaluation of the assumptions made in the risk assessment process should also be communicated. Note that tacit assumptions have the potential to obscure a major aspect of the risk (see section 3 for more on the role of assumptions).

However, DNV stated that it is not always appropriate or indeed useful to communicate risk using quantitative methods (see also section 4 and 5.1). Even if a quantitative analysis is possible it may not be necessary, sometimes it is sufficient to provide a qualitative description of the risk to support a decision. On occasions where it is necessary to be more precise, the precision of the risk description should match what is supported by the knowledge.

5.4 Climate interventions: Red Cross - Red Crescent Climate Centre

The mission of the Climate Centre is to support the Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement and its partners in reducing the impacts of climate change and extreme-weather events on vulnerable people. Christopher Jack is a climate science expert with the Climate Centre who is primarily engaged with forecast based finance and anticipatory action. Chris has become increasingly involved and passionate about integrating climate science into collaborative learning, co-production, and transdisciplinary action research processes. We are grateful to Chris for sharing his experience in this field with the Communicating Climate Uncertainty workshop held by Climateurope2.

Humanitarian Sector

Aid interventions in the humanitarian sector aim to limit the impact of rapidly emerging and evolving crises by anticipating emerging and evolving crises over weeks through months and possibly years. The humanitarian sector is characterised by high complexity with compounding and cascading risks and impact, high uncertainty with low quality or no data related to vulnerability as well as climate, and a high cost of failure. Failure to anticipate impacts can cost a lot more than acting in anticipation. The mis-allocation of funding and resources can cost lives. Within complex humanitarian contexts the relative contribution of weather and climate compared to other factors influencing a crisis is not always clear.

Development Sector

Aid interventions in the development sector aim to enable, support and encourage development in the face of climate variability and long-term change. The development sector is characterised by high complexity of climate risk governance (Who makes what decisions? Where does the money come from? There are multiple and contested agendas), and high uncertainty with lots of actors including

consultants and climate service providers. From a user perspective there is uncertainty about where to get information (who to listen to and which portal to use). Therefore, building trust and relationships is very important (who to trust and why to trust them).

Anticipatory Action

With anticipatory action, a warning of a crisis event allows action to be taken before the impacts occur. Forecast based Finance (FbF) is an example of an Early Action Plan (EAP) mechanism that enables disaster preparedness through humanitarian funding for early action based on in-depth forecast information and risk analysis. The release of funds to trigger early actions is agreed in advance and is based on forecasts exceeding specific thresholds (figure 5.6).

Figure 5.6: Early Action Plan (EAP) validation steps (Heinrich and Bailey, 2020).

1. Risk assessment. Historical impact reports are used to identify risks, however, there remains a lot of uncertainty about how events impact communities. Impact reports require a broad participatory process involving national meteorological services and disaster management agencies collaborating with government and communities to identify beneficiaries (Who is most vulnerable? Who will benefit the most?). Broad involvement is used to achieve collectively supported decisions.

2. Identify forecasts. Forecasts from local institutions are prioritised as they will have a mandate and early warning systems in place. Trust in and a sense of ownership of local forecasts can be more important than forecast skill.

3. Define impact level. When will we trigger? The funding can't support lots of false alarms so organizations aim to trigger only for high impact (1 in 5 years) events. Forecast skill may require accepting a certain number of false alarms or misses. It is important to collectively agree on an acceptable probability of false alarms and misses as these can degrade trust if the approach is not collectively owned. Collective agreement is difficult but is a core tenant of managing uncertainty in this context.

7. Multiple flexible triggers. Some uncertainty can be managed by using multiplied staged triggers. The first trigger has a higher false alarm rate but activates low cost preparedness actions. The second trigger has a lower false alarm rate and may even be a STOP that halts action. Flexible triggering moves away from "objective" triggers and allows for expert consensus on triggering. This allows for unanticipated factors not captured by the trigger model to be included (e.g. emerging conflict).

Transparency and trust

Communication formats should **transparently** convey the nature of uncertainty being communicated and be readily comprehensible to ensure that decisions can be made based on an understanding of the uncertainties. Traditional, scientific formats for communicating uncertainty, such as technical graphs, can be difficult for non-scientists to comprehend. Although simplified information may be more easily understood, it may not provide sufficient depth of information to inform decisions. Finding the right balance may be best achieved using co-production (Coventry et al., 2019).

Trust in climate information and those who communicate information should be measured and evaluated to assess how communication and engagement activities influence trust in information. Stakeholders often equate uncertainty with 'not knowing' and/or a lack of accuracy. This can reduce trust in using the information and in turn prevent action. Measuring trust can help identify communication approaches that foster shared understandings of uncertainty (Coventry et al., 2019).

Climate risk narratives and storylines

There is strong evidence that people use narratives to capture the essential meaning of complex evidence (see also section 3). When presented with complexity, people gravitate towards constructing a narrative. Even if someone is presented with a scientific graph, what they take away will be a narrative about what the graph means, and that meaning will be different for different people. Just as risk is different for different people, the way they engage with complexity is different too. People also tend to hold on to existing narratives and seek evidence that confirms these (confirmation bias).

Figure 5.7: Understanding existing risk narratives and the co-creation of new climate risk narratives and adaptation pathways towards climate resilience for informal settlements in Lusaka, Zambia. Climate science information was presented during this process, such as flood maps from high resolution modelling, but it was available as print-outs on the walls and did not drive the narrative.

Collaboratively developing climate risk narratives or storylines begins by taking time to understand existing narratives within a particular decision context (figure 5.7). Until a climate communication practitioner understands existing narratives and how people are thinking about risk and decision making within these spaces it is very hard to introduce climate information. Once a practitioner has an idea of existing narratives, trust can be built through mutual learning, embracing the diversity and contradictions of people with competing views and understanding. Working with humility and transparency is needed to co-create new Climate Risk Narratives.

Climate scientists need to understand that they bring only one part of the information into a complex context. The climate component is not superior or dominant compared to other parts of the context. Therefore, scientists need to work collaboratively to decide how to interrogate the uncertainty of climate model projections and allow everyone to engage with the assumptions that are made. For instance, average rainfall changes were not considered to be the main concern for Lusaka and so were not included in the scenario analysis.

Many of the responses to the different climate risk scenarios were very similar (once the decision spaces and funding constraints had been worked through) (figure 5.8), so perceived uncertainty about what action to take to build resilience became clearer.

Figure 5.8: Climate Risk Narratives / Storylines for Lusaka, Zambia for three scenarios: 1. Hotter & drier, 2. Warmer & more erratic and extreme rainfall, 3. Warmer & more extreme rainfall.

Two strong pathways emerged: a strong engineering/planning pathway with a flood masterplan and large-scale drainage, and a separate pathway focused on local governance: who is involved in decision making? Local area development planning, was followed up with financial resources to enable locally lead implementation.

The climate risk narrative/storylines process resulted in shifts in local climate governance. Groundwater recharge conservation areas were implemented. Finance was allocated to local ward development committees to address local climate risks (e.g. flooding) in ways that they felt were appropriate. And a community of practitioners was built that included city officials who were engaged in the decision making and had a positive impact.

Good decisions

Recognising that in general each decision maker has different demands – even those in the same geographical location and in the same sector, e.g. two farmers with adjacent plots planning to plant the same crop but considering different types of seeds-, “good” or “bad” decisions can mean completely different things.

Assuming that the demand has been correctly identified, and hence what is beneficial (“good”) in order to satisfy that demand, at the end of the day “good” decisions are what is aimed for.. But what are good decisions?

Any communication of climate information should be informed by an understanding of:

- How decisions (especially assumptions on the pathway from science to decision making) are really made and by who.
- How risk is already perceived and managed, heterogeneity is difficult to capture in risk models.
- What the implications of “bad” decisions are.

Climate communication is deeply entangled with trust, humility, mutual learning and contested perspectives. How to do this communication within a standardised approach of climate services in the face of contextual complexity and differing perspectives remains a challenge.

5.5 Uncertainty communication across timescales

Table 5.2: Overview of strategies for communicating climate data uncertainty across timescales.

Time scale	Communication Strategies
Historical climate	<p>Include lived experience: Add year-to-year historical variability to statistical graphs of the historical period to help the audience understand the statistical graphs that describe the projected future climates.</p> <p>Storylines: event-based storylines can provide a useful way of communicating and assessing compound climate-related risks. The self-consistent unfolding of past events can be used to inform plausible future events or pathways.</p>
Seasonal prediction	<p>Vulnerabilities: Explore vulnerabilities to discover which climate risks are of most concern.</p>

<p>(months to ~1 year)</p>	<p>Early Action Plans: Some uncertainty can be managed by using multiple staged triggers for anticipatory action in a humanitarian/development context. The first trigger has a higher false alarm rate but activates low cost preparedness actions. Subsequent triggers have lower false alarm rates and allow for unanticipated factors not captured by the trigger model to be included. Collectively agree on an acceptable probability of false alarms and misses as these can degrade trust if the approach is not collectively owned.</p> <p>Maps: Convey uncertainty by presenting more than one map. To avoid the implicit assumption that data presented as a percentage change is true for the whole of an area rather than being specific to a locality, present climate indices using their absolute values.</p> <p>Decision support: Even if a quantitative analysis is possible it may not be necessary, sometimes it is sufficient to provide a qualitative description of the risk to support a decision.</p>
<p>Decadal prediction (1–10 years)</p>	<p>Deep uncertainty: the inability to assign precise probabilities to future events or to fully comprehend the system's complexity. More uncertainty is a reason to take a risk more seriously. It can be helpful to convey deep uncertainty via storylines for a range of scenarios.</p>
<p>Long-term climate projections (multi-decadal to century)</p>	<p>Establish the idea of uncertainty: Include more than one scenario for future climate - preferably an even number of scenarios.</p> <p>Include lived experience: Add year-to-year historical variability to statistical graphs of the historical period to help the audience to understand the statistical graphs that describe the projected future climates.</p> <p>Storylines: event-based storylines can provide a useful way of communicating and assessing compound climate-related risks. The self-consistent unfolding of past events can be used to inform plausible future events or pathways.</p> <p>Language of uncertainty: be aware that scientific terms can have a very different meaning in public life, e.g. rather than using the word “uncertainty” which implies ignorance, a better choice could be the word “range”.</p>

6 Climate service provision by the private sector

There are a growing number of climate services provided by the private sector. This community understands the requirements of their users well and build tools which provide them with the specific information they need. The building blocks of these tools are the climate data in public archives such as the CMIP data used to inform the IPCC assessment process.

This section presents perspectives on uncertainty in the provision of climate services, based on interviews with three European private providers. The interviews were conducted individually—two online and one in person—then transcribed manually, analysed, and distilled into key messages. To ensure transparency, AI tools were used only to refine the writing style after the messages had been drafted. The resulting text was then carefully revised against the original transcripts, and finally validated by the companies themselves before publication. The guiding interview questions can be found in the Annex of this document.

For better understandability, the key messages have been structured in five main blocks with respective subtopics:

- Uncertainty quantification
 - Model ensembles
 - Scenarios
 - Economics
- Uncertainty communication
 - Format
 - Scenarios
 - Visual cues
- Co-production and training
 - Clients' background
 - Clients' request
- How can standardisation help? (or not)
 - Communication methods, phrasing, and vocabulary
 - Regulation and standardization – advantages
 - Regulation and standardization – disadvantages
 - Standardization – considerations
- Trustability / Openness / Transparency
 - Publication in peer-reviewed journals
 - Proprietary knowledge
 - Competition and comparison between providers
 - Clients' rights and responsibilities

Of course, there is some unavoidable overlap between topics, and thus we recommend the interested reader to go through all sections.

Disclaimer – The opinions presented here do not necessarily reflect the views of all companies in the sector, may evolve over time, and should not be interpreted as the position of the authors of this document. In addition, given the limited scope of this work, the results should not be considered statistically representative of the market as a whole.

Nevertheless, we believe that this effort contributes to bridging the persistent gap between the private and public sectors, which rarely exchange views despite the clear need to do so in order to

build an ecosystem that benefits all. This process will continue until early 2026, when we will share final results as part of the Climateurope2 project, specifically Deliverable D2.8. We warmly invite additional providers, both public and private, to contribute with their perspectives.

Finally, we gratefully acknowledge the time and expertise shared with us by the following providers: [Meteoclim del Grupo WDNA](#), [Geoskop](#), and [Eoliann](#).

6.1 Uncertainty quantification

Climate models and scenarios are the largest source of uncertainty in climate services.

Uncertainty is difficult to measure or clearly define, in part because climate science involves “deep uncertainty”—unknowns that cannot be easily quantified.

Some providers address this by emphasizing **precision, accuracy, and skill** instead of uncertainty itself. These terms are sometimes mistakenly used as if they were the same as uncertainty. In practice, demonstrating skill usually requires comparing results against a “sufficiently large” historical period. The aim is to show that a method performs better than existing alternatives and therefore adds value to the customer.

There is no single method that works best everywhere or at all times. Services that apply the same method worldwide can deliver information efficiently and consistently, but may fall short compared to specialised approaches tailored to a region or sector.

Different industries also have different priorities. For instance, banks may only be interested in the statistical performance of a portfolio of assets. In contrast, infrastructure planners focus on identifying the weakest points in a system, since that is what determines vulnerability.

6.1.1 Model ensembles

Model ensembles are often used to express uncertainty by looking at how different models distribute their results. But selecting models for an ensemble is not straightforward. Ideally, an ensemble should represent the full range of accepted scientific approaches to modeling the Earth system. In practice, some ensembles are “ensembles of opportunity,” meaning they contain models that were not originally designed to work together. This can create challenges, such as overlapping models that share components.

Another open question is how much weight to assign to each model. Many providers note that they lack detailed information about the models and ensembles, which makes it harder to choose appropriate post-processing methods. Greater transparency on assumptions, overlaps, parameters, and intended uses would improve the usefulness of ensembles.

6.1.2 Scenarios

The choice of scenarios and their underlying assumptions is a major source of deep uncertainty.

Not all clients need all scenarios, and their preferences often relate to the **principle of prudence**—the idea of avoiding over-optimism in planning. For example, in services designed to save lives during extreme events, it is essential to describe the worst-case outcomes. Ignoring them would mean overlooking lives that could otherwise be protected. This principle, however, can be undermined when data is smoothed or averaged across large, diverse areas, or when thresholds are set without reflecting local differences.

In the scenarios published by the IPCC, projections related to temperature are generally more reliable than those for other variables or tipping points. This imbalance reduces confidence in scenarios as a whole and makes it harder to combine multiple variables in comprehensive risk assessments.

6.1.3 Economics

Budget constraints strongly influence which methods are used in climate services—and therefore also affect uncertainty. Choices such as whether to use dynamical or statistical downscaling, how many models to include in an ensemble, or how extensively to validate results against historical data are all limited by available resources.

6.2 Uncertainty communication

The way climate information is worded and phrased matters greatly. Messages need to be precise, concise, and carefully expressed. What is said—and how it is said—shapes how clients interpret and use the information. Since clients come from diverse sectors, with different needs, backgrounds, and expectations, the same technical vocabulary may not work for everyone. In fact, the established climate terminology can be difficult to understand outside specialist circles. In some cases, information is adapted to align with the jargon and communication style of the sector being addressed.

6.2.1 Format

Lengthy emails and detailed reports are rarely effective. Meetings, infographics, visual cues, and engaging interactive graphics often communicate the message far more efficiently.

Today's communication culture favors quick, visual formats—such as short videos or reels where complex ideas are condensed into brief explanations. Climate communication needs to take into account this cultural environment. Visual and aesthetic appeal should not be disregarded.

Simple traffic-light style outputs are popular: they are visually appealing, easy to understand, and widely used for audiences without deep climate expertise. However, they also carry risks. Oversimplification can be misleading, and such tools should never be the sole basis for high-stakes decisions involving millions of dollars, nor decisions related to human lives.

6.2.2 Scenarios

When presenting scenarios, a comparative or relative analysis often works better than quoting absolute numbers. This helps audiences grasp differences and trends without getting lost in technical detail.

6.2.3 Visual cues

Colors are powerful communication tools, making complex information easier to interpret. For instance, green is widely understood as “good” and red as “bad.” But caution is needed: color choices can reinforce oversimplifications, create misleading expectations, fall into viewer-bias, or exclude people with color blindness. Effective use of colors requires balance—highlighting key messages without distorting the meaning.

6.3 Co-production and training

Climate services are usually developed in **co-production** with clients, meaning they are tailored to specific needs through a collaborative process. This process is often long, involves continuous learning, and works best when providers remain humble and open.

From the provider's side, feedback from clients is regularly collected and used to improve both the content and the way information is delivered. However, one recurring challenge is finding the person responsible for climate risk within a client's organization. Few companies have a dedicated climate department, and risk managers often do not yet see the value of climate information—or are unsure how to integrate it into their processes.

6.3.1 Clients' background

Clients who are new to climate services are particularly **vulnerable**. They may not know what to ask for—because it is hard to define what you want if you don't yet understand what is possible. This makes them more susceptible to confident, persuasive messages, even if those messages oversimplify the reality.

Misunderstandings are common, and part of the learning process. For example, a colored map with grid cells every kilometer may look straightforward, but it could represent either interpolated observations or results from a complex physical model—two very different things.

Skepticism also plays a role. Large climate models often have a poor reputation among non-experts. A common question is: "If weather forecasts can be wrong, how can we trust climate projections?" Addressing this requires careful explanation of the difference between predicting short-term weather and modeling long-term climate trends.

For providers, the challenge lies in communicating clearly with people who may have little background knowledge. Successful communication happens when both sides start "speaking the same language." Some sectors are already familiar with climate data, which makes this process faster. In other sectors, more time, training and adaptation are needed.

6.3.2 Clients' requests

Clients rarely approach providers with a clear idea of what format or product they need. They usually know they want climate information, but not the specifics.

Most clients are interested in **projections up to 20 years ahead**. Beyond that, trust tends to decline, either because the data is seen as too uncertain or because clients feel they cannot realistically make decisions so far into the future.

Expectations around uncertainty vary widely. Some clients prefer to avoid it altogether, wanting only the simplest possible outputs. Others take the opposite view: the more detail provided, the more valuable the information becomes, because they can build on it. There are also mixed cases:

Some want uncertainty quantified at every grid cell.

Others only want broad metrics describing potential change, distribution, or extent over time.

Some know they want uncertainty included, but are unsure of the form it should take.

In many cases, clients focus less on uncertainty itself and more on precision, accuracy, and skill. Some even test providers through pilot projects: they supply a dataset and expect the provider to demonstrate results that outperform their existing methods.

6.4 How can standardisation help? (or not)

6.4.1 Communication methods, phrasing, and vocabulary

Vague or overly emotional wording can be misleading. It also makes it harder for clients to compare different services. Clear phrasing guidelines for providers could help customers better understand what each service offers, manage expectations, and highlight the unique value proposition of each provider.

Messages should be **understandable by a broad audience—even children**. At the same time, definitions should not be so rigid that they limit innovation in the very methods they aim to describe.

Vocabulary also differs widely between industries. While certain climate-specific terms can be standardised, once communication moves into resilience and sector-specific risks, the language often becomes less precise and harder to unify. Any effort at standardization should therefore be developed **in collaboration with private sector actors and market players**, to ensure it reflects real needs and practices.

6.4.2 Regulation and standardisation — advantages

From the client's perspective, regulation and standardization can bring a number of benefits. They raise awareness and help define the minimum information that should be delivered, ensuring that at least a baseline of quality is met. Once services are standardised, their price often decreases, making them more accessible. At the same time, standardization can increase trust, for example by introducing certification systems that distinguish between different levels of quality according to the effort and methodology used. This kind of certification not only justifies different price levels but also allows companies to position themselves in different parts of the market. Smaller firms and startups, in particular, could gain credibility from such systems, as official standards would give them a stronger basis to demonstrate their value in comparison with larger corporations.

6.4.3 Regulation and standardisation — disadvantages

There are also clear downsides. If climate services become too similar under a standardised framework, the market risks sliding into commoditization, where every provider delivers the same minimum product. This drives prices and profits down, which in turn can force smaller providers out of the market, reduce competition, and leave space mainly for large corporations. In such a scenario, innovation suffers, because there is little incentive to go beyond the minimum requirements. Some fear that regulation would shift the market toward compliance-driven “regtech” products, designed mainly to satisfy rules rather than to improve climate services themselves. Certification processes, if they are too slow or rigid, could also become an obstacle, especially for small and fast-moving companies. Moreover, there is an argument that startups are already able to compete effectively without such certifications, and that additional layers of bureaucracy would not add value.

6.4.4 Standardisation — considerations

Even if regulation and standardization are pursued, important questions remain. How can standardisation be made downstream when upstream there are still efforts to be made? For example, the provision of information through climate model ensembles is not yet fully standardised, which raises doubts about how far downstream services can be expected to align. It is also important to remember that many clients approach smaller companies because they want more than simple compliance; they are looking for tailored services and additional insights. This leads to a deeper question: what exactly should be the objective of standardization? If the goal is to guarantee the same level of quality everywhere, for any user at any time, is this something climate science can realistically provide? And even if it can, how do we define “quality” in a way that works across all sectors?

Existing resources already provide partial answers. Organizations such as ECMWF and C3S have developed robust libraries that many providers treat as guidelines or informal standards. One option

could be to require companies that choose not to use these resources to make that clear to clients. In terms of climate model ensembles, the CMIP framework already functions like an international standard, similar to an ISO, by enforcing specific formats and protocols. In addition, the IPCC already offers some guidelines on how to communicate uncertainty and what wording to use. These examples show that parts of the system are already standardised, which raises further questions about where additional regulation is truly necessary.

6.5 Trustability / openness / transparency

An important question for climate service providers is whether they would be willing to link their own success to that of their clients—for example, by earning money only when their service leads to profits. Many companies would not accept such terms, which highlights the difference between offering information and taking on business risk. Some voices in the field argue that providers should not be afraid of communicating openly about the limits of their work, including acknowledging that uncertainty is both very large and extremely difficult to quantify. There is also increasing demand for companies that promote “magical” algorithms or deliver purely qualitative outputs to demonstrate how they validate their results. Transparency about validation is essential to build trust.

6.5.1 Publication in peer-reviewed journals

Publishing in peer-reviewed journals can help strengthen credibility and foster trust, but the picture is not entirely straightforward. Even when providers are willing to publish, not all types of data or sources can be openly shared. The degree of openness in scientific journals also varies: publishing does not always mean being fully transparent about every aspect of a service. Moreover, methodologies evolve over time, which means that what was described in a paper a few years ago may no longer reflect the current practice. This creates a gap between published material and the living, evolving methods that providers use in their services.

6.5.2 Proprietary knowledge

Some companies choose to protect their intellectual property through strict industrial secrecy, keeping everything developed in-house under tight control. Confidentiality agreements allow them to disclose more detail to clients when necessary, but here too, openness exists in shades of grey. In practice, keeping knowledge proprietary rarely prevents companies from attracting new clients, since high-level information is usually sufficient. In fact, as mentioned earlier in the context of client requests, some customers test providers directly by running pilot projects, offering their own data and asking the provider to demonstrate that their results outperform the client’s current state of the art.

6.5.3 Competition and comparison between providers

Competition between providers often touches on the question of transparency. Some companies complain that others are not open enough, and suggest that if all methodologies were clearly laid out, it would be easier to see which approach is stronger. Cultural differences also shape how providers present themselves. In some countries, humility in communication is mistaken for weakness or uncertainty, while in Europe clients increasingly see humility as a mark of seriousness and credibility. Another issue arises in the context of regionalisation and downscaling, where providers debate whether complex new techniques should be openly disclosed. The discussion becomes even sharper when artificial intelligence is involved, since many clients view AI methods as a “black box.”

6.5.4 Clients’ rights and responsibilities

Clients ultimately have the right to make informed decisions based on the services they receive. This makes clear documentation not just useful, but in many cases essential, and some argue it should even be compulsory. To protect both sides, some providers include disclaimers that customers must sign,

confirming that they understand the type of data they are receiving and the risks associated with its use. Such practices underline the shared responsibility between provider and client in managing climate information and the decisions built upon it.

7 Concluding Comments: Emerging Themes

This section includes concluding remarks, in the form of key “emerging themes” or lessons learnt. A lot of work has been done in the scientific community to describe sources of uncertainty and quantify uncertainty where this is possible. Also, sophisticated ways have been developed to visualise uncertainties. However, communicating about these uncertainties to users outside of the scientific community remains a huge challenge. Some efforts have been made, for example, by the IPCC but this issue is far from being solved. From this exercise we gather the following ways forward:

Start with the most relevant risks

An exploration of vulnerabilities can be used to discover which climate risks are of most concern. From there a climate communication practitioner (ideally in collaboration with the clients they are supporting) can discern which aspects of climate information are most relevant to those risks and hence the relevant uncertainty space to describe. To support the work of climate communication practitioners a climate service provider will need to provide sufficient information about its data holdings to enable the relevant uncertainty information to be extracted.

Standard approach to uncertainty descriptions

The scope of climate science is broad. The implications of its findings need to be understood by many different research communities and also be communicated to wider society. A standard approach to describing and quantifying uncertainty will facilitate the passing of information between different communities of practice. Such an approach should consider not only the climate science component, but also the complexities regarding socio-economic vulnerability, and hence social sciences should be involved.

Use language the audience is familiar with (don't say uncertainty)

The vocabulary of science can have very different meanings in public life. Therefore, when dealing with climate services and decision makers, it is usually better to use commonly understood descriptive language in place of scientific terminology, along with multiple contextualised examples illustrating the concepts and approaches. Particular care should be taken with uncertainty communication, for instance, rather than using the word “uncertainty” which implies ignorance, a better choice could be the word “range”, and rather than presenting a likelihood as a percentage instead refer to it using the framing of odds.

There are multiple ways to evaluate and communicate uncertainty

Decision makers require the best, reliable information to optimally accomplish their job. Although a measure of uncertainty must be always conveyed, there are multiple ways to measure and communicate it. The most used way is to communicate uncertainty via probabilities of occurrence (or not occurrence) of a certain event, but very often decision makers consider the use of odds -and relative odds- more understandable and actionable than actual probabilities. It is also possible to communicate uncertainty by a combination of the expected value (e.g. the ensemble median) and uncertainty bars (e.g. the ensemble interquartile range). In other contexts, it may be more appropriate not to communicate probabilistic information at all and instead explore the use of plausible storylines to help communicate climate risk and highlight specific vulnerabilities.

Use communication about uncertainty to build trust

The existence of high uncertainty should be seen as a reason to engage with information, particularly if it relates to a vulnerability. Climate services should be transparent about the uncertainty evaluation of their information. With an awareness of uncertainties comes an ability to assess risks more

critically. More confidence can be placed in assessments of risk that are clear, in spite of the uncertainties.

Precision of information should be relevant to the situation

General statements of uncertainty can be sufficient. Even if a quantitative analysis is possible it may not be necessary. The precision of a risk description should match what is needed. The presenting of high resolution data will lead audiences to assume a high degree of certainty that may not be justified. Risk descriptions should match what the knowledge supports.

Understand existing narratives

People use narratives to capture the essential meaning of complex evidence. Until the existing narratives and how people are thinking about risk and decision making are well understood, it is very hard to introduce actionable climate information and related services. Once there is a clear idea of existing narratives, it is key to build trust through mutual learning, embrace the diversity and contradictions of people with competing views and understanding, and work with humility and transparency to co-create new climate risk narratives or storylines of plausible future events.

Be aware of deep uncertainties

The conventional approach to representing uncertainty in climate services is probabilistic, typically based on ensembles of climate model simulations. In the face of deep uncertainties, the limitations of this approach are becoming increasingly apparent. It is therefore important to extend existing methodologies to include strategies for accounting for and communicating deep uncertainty, including the recording of assumptions made in the analysis process and evaluating the impact of these on the final outcome or decision, and the co-creation of narratives or storylines to improve risk awareness and strengthen decision-making.

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9 Annex

9.1 Interview questions

The interview questions are structured in 5 blocks:

- Introductory questions
- Understanding the climate service
- Uncertainty questions
- Challenges and expectations
- Closing questions

Introductory questions

Objective: Get contextual information about the interviewee, and the project, service, company, or institution he/she is going to talk about.

- **Personal context**
Get to know the background of the interviewee.
 - Could you please give us an overview of your background and your current position?
- **Climate service context**
Clarify the topic of the interview, i.e., identify the project/service/company the interviewee is going to discuss
 - Could you please briefly describe the project/sector/company you will be discussing during this interview?
 - What's the purpose of the climate service you are providing?
 - What is your role in the service/process?
- **Service participants and beneficiaries**
Identify the system of actors taking part in the climate service.
 - Could you please explain the chain of participants/actors in your climate service?
 - Who is funding the service?
 - Who are the final users of the service?
 - What is/are the decisions that the service is informing or supporting?

Understanding the climate service

Objective: better understand the details of the climate service

- **Temporal context**
 - What is the timeframe of the provision/service we are talking about?
- **Data flow**
 - What type of data do you use as input?
 - What type of data do you provide?
 - What are the processing steps that you apply to the data?
- **Service content**
 - Are you providing analysis services?
 - Is the role of your service to re-present existing information?
 - Do you provide information about extreme events?
- **Service provision**
 - How do you communicate or provide your service to the users?

Uncertainty questions

Objective: understand how uncertainty is accounted for and communicated

- What do you think are the biggest sources of uncertainty in your processing chain?
- Do your communication methods include provision for uncertainty? (*see also the add-on examples below to elaborate if necessary*)
- Do your uncertainty communication methods distinguish between different audiences?
 - Do you group your audiences into categories for communication design?
- Have you tested your communication methods? Are they co-developed with users?
- Do you include qualitative and/or quantitative methods?
 - How are these combined in your communications?
- Do you communicate choices and assumptions that are made in the data processing to your users? And if so, how?

Examples to tag onto these questions:

- Do you present ensemble information?
- Do you present scenario information?
- Do you infer uncertainty via interactive products?
- Do you cater for general or specific audiences?

Challenges and expectations

Objective: understand the challenges people experience, and their expectations from standardisation

- **Lessons learned & shared experience**
 - Have you tried different approaches to deal with and communicate uncertainty?
 - What works in uncertainty communication? What didn't work?
 - What do you see as the biggest challenge in this context?
- **Standardisation**
 - How can standardised climate services help with accounting for and communicating uncertainty?
 - Is there a need for standardised approaches to uncertainty communication?
 - Would you benefit from guidelines or advice on dealing with and communicating uncertainty?

Closing questions

- Is there anything else you would like to share?